

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF THE MEMORY PROCESS IN LEARNING
THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article presents theoretical information about the importance of memory in learning English in children of small school age, and the benefits of early language learning. In addition, the steps related to the memory process of the development of the English language, the formation of language learning skills in the period of junior school age and its schedule are covered in a practical way.

Keywords: early childhood education, early childhood, English language development, language learning skills.

Introduction. In our country today, it is necessary to form the knowledge and skills of schoolchildren, educate them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, establish modern models of school education institutions that meet international standards, and the responsibility of teachers in providing education and training to young people. , increasing the demand for continuous professional development, meaningful organization of students' free time, improving the system of directing them to professions is one of the most urgent issues. For this purpose, the period of junior school age is considered one of the most sensitive periods of formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities. The period of junior school age includes periods from 6-7 to 9-10 years. During this period, the child gets acquainted with the various requirements of schoolchildren, is biologically and psychologically prepared to learn the basics of science. The psyche of a child during this period develops to the extent that it can acquire knowledge.

The main part. A child of junior school age is distinguished from other children by his sharpness of perception, clarity, purity, accuracy, his curiosity, trustworthiness, vivid expression of his imagination, the breadth of his memory's receptiveness, and the clear expression of his thinking. In a child preparing for school education, the process of attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable. The main activity of children of primary school age is studying. A child's going to school plays an important role in his psychological development and personality formation. Under the guidance of the teacher, the child learns the content of various basic forms of human consciousness and learns to act on the basis of human traditions. In the study activity, the child exercises his will to achieve educational goals. Reading activity requires the child to develop speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking processes to the required level, and creates new conditions and opportunities for the development of the child's personality. A child who comes to school for the first time psychologically moves to a new system of interpersonal relations with those around him. He begins to feel that his life has changed radically, that he has new obligations, not only to go to school every day, but also to obey the demands of academic activities. The fact that the child is interested in the academic activities and achievements of his family members, as well as controlling him, the new treatment and interpersonal relations that are given to him, make him fully feel that his social status has changed, and the child's attitude towards

himself. serves as a basis for change. Adults teach school-aged children to study well, engage in play activities, go for walks, and engage in other types of activities. Thus, the child occupies a new place in the family where he is counted and consulted. The student's success at school is considered a completely positive basis for his further mental development and the formation of personality traits.

Second language education has been steadily increasing throughout the world as a result of early childhood education. As the demand for learning a foreign language increases, parents who love their children and want them to have modern knowledge at birth for the sake of their future, are becoming more interested in teaching their children a language from elementary school age.

Early childhood education sets the stage for lifelong learning and cognitive development. A key aspect of early education is long-term memory development, ensuring that what children learn today stays with them throughout their lives. The ability to remember and apply previously learned information is an important indicator of academic success. A strong long-term memory allows children to build on what they have learned in earlier stages of education and makes it easier for them to grasp advanced concepts. The development of memory is a process that develops throughout a person's life, and the development of memory in children is evident in the first 3 years of a child's life, because they make significant progress in the child's memory throughout the development of declarative memory.

Results and discussion. In this case, it is better for parents to introduce their children to a second language as early as possible. It is the best time to teach children a language at the age of 3-4, because children at this age differ in terms of memory and speech and absorb information very well, and because their brain is actively developing, language learning strengthens brain activity.

Learning a second language does not have a negative effect on the child's mother tongue, on the contrary, bilingual children have the ability to distinguish between languages from an early age.

Early language learning benefits include:

- Learning a language improves the child's brain activity;
- Enables better understanding of other cultures;
- The ability to hear and remember will be stronger;
- When he grows up, he becomes confident that he will be able to learn other languages;
- Has a strong vocabulary;

Conclusion. Language development in children is a process of acquiring the ability to understand and communicate through speech. It is considered one of the best solutions to start the stages of development of language skills in children before the transition to junior school age, i.e., from preschool age, and in this period, listing the following stages of language skills development and putting them into practice is of great importance. is considered They are:

- Before starting the study, you, like your child, are interested in this language;
- Finding a good book for language teaching;
- Watch a fairy tale or cartoon related to the language your child is learning and explain its meaning;
- Children get tired quickly, so the training process should not exceed 30-40 minutes;
- Use of game methods during the lesson;
- Use of game methodology for training;

□ Explain the topic sitting with the children on the carpet, not standing up as much as possible.

Based on the above, the earlier the formation of foreign language skills begins, the greater the chance of success.

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